

RISERS Working Groups Fact Sheet

Introduction

The RISERS project (“A Roadmap for Industrial Symbiosis Standardisation for Efficient Resource Sharing”) is dedicated to guiding the standardisation of industrial symbiosis to enhance resource efficiency across Europe. Launched under the European Union’s Horizon Europe Programme, RISERS aims to address standardisation gaps and overcome barriers hindering efficient resource sharing. By collaborating with experts and practitioners from various sectors—including industry, policy, academia, and standardisation bodies—the project seeks to provide a comprehensive roadmap that will steer industrial symbiosis standardisation efforts in Europe toward greater efficiency and sustainability. This roadmap will be developed through an iterative and collaborative process, combining stakeholder input, thematic Working Groups, and expert analysis.

For more information visit our website: www.risers-project.eu

RISERS

The RISERS Working Groups (WGs)

The RISERS Working Groups (WGs) support the development of a **standardisation roadmap for industrial symbiosis (IS)** by addressing key thematic areas and synergies. They serve as a structured yet open platform for advancing industrial symbiosis standardisation. Their main objectives are to:

- Identify challenges, gaps, and opportunities in IS standardisation, shaping roadmap priorities.
- Highlight barriers in existing standards and policy frameworks.
- Recommend best practices, guidelines, and standardisation actions.

The results will be shared with standardisation committees to support future standards in industrial symbiosis.

Structure & Approach

1. **10 Pre-defined Working Groups** – 3 cross-cutting & 7 thematic, based on 600+ mapped IS cases and expert input.
2. **Flexible & Collaborative** – WGs are free to define key synergies and priorities and are open to new experts.
3. **Action-Oriented** – Focused on delivering clear, impactful standardisation outcomes.

Cross-cutting WGs

WG 01: IS in General

Focuses on system-level enablers of industrial symbiosis across sectors. It explores governance models, business frameworks, and standardisation for resource efficiency and circular economy strategies.

WG 02: End-of-Waste

Addresses the transition from waste to resource by harmonizing End-of-Waste criteria across the EU. It aims to standardise definitions, quality requirements, and cross-border recognition of secondary materials.

WG 03: Digitalisation & Data

Explores how data and digital tools enable industrial symbiosis. Focuses on interoperability, governance, and standards for data sharing, monitoring, and digital twins to optimise resource flows across industries.

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WGs for key thematic areas & sectors

WG 04: Steel, Slag & Refractories

Investigates industrial symbiosis in steel production, focusing on steel scrap/waste steel recovery, slag, fly ash, and refractory recycling. It seeks to standardise classification, reuse criteria, and material valorisation in construction and cement.

For more reading consult the RISERS fact-sheets:

- 🔗 Waste Steel Synergy Fact-sheet
- 🔗 BOF/EOF Slag Synergy Fact-sheet
- 🔗 Refractory Materials Synergy Fact-sheet

WG 05: Batteries

Focuses on battery reuse, recycling, and critical raw material recovery. Explores standardisation for dismantling, second-life applications, and cross-sector reuse to enhance circularity and resource security.

For more reading consult the RISERS fact-sheet:

- 🔗 EV-Batteries Synergy Fact-sheet

WG 06: Packaging

Examines circular packaging solutions, including reuse and recycling. Addresses industrial and consumer packaging, standardisation for traceability, sorting, and compliance with EU regulations like PPWR.

For more reading consult the RISERS fact-sheet:

- 🔗 Plastic Packaging Synergy Fact-sheet

WG 07: Waste Heat

Targets waste heat recovery for industrial and urban applications. Focuses on technical and regulatory barriers, standardisation for heat classification, monitoring, and integration with district heating networks.

For more reading consult the RISERS fact-sheet:

- 🔗 Waste Heat Synergy Fact-sheet

WG 08: Textiles

Promotes textile waste recycling and reuse. Explores quality standards for recycled fibers, traceability systems, and alignment with EU policies to support fiber-to-fiber recycling and circular design.

For more reading consult the RISERS fact-sheet:

- 🔗 Textiles Synergy Fact-sheet

WG 09: Energy Data & Grids

Addresses energy data exchange and grid flexibility. Focuses on standards for interoperability, demand-response participation, cybersecurity, and integrating industrial symbiosis with energy systems.

For more reading consult the RISERS fact-sheet:

- 🔗 Energy Data Synergy Fact-sheet

WG 10: Biomass & Waste Wood

Explores biomass valorisation for energy, materials, and bio-based products. Standardises biomass classification, sustainable sourcing, cascading use, and emissions control in industrial symbiosis networks.

For more reading consult the RISERS fact-sheets:

- 🔗 Biomass Residues Synergy Fact-sheet
- 🔗 Biomass Synergy Fact-sheet

What's next?

1

Kick-off Working Group Discussions
Start defining challenges, gaps, and standardisation needs during WG Meetings Round 1 (April–May 2025)

2

Deliver Interim Inputs
WG outputs from Round 1 will feed into the **Draft Roadmap Outline**
Contributions to be presented at the **Plenary (5 June 2025)**

3

Refine & Validate Recommendations
WG Meetings Round 2 (Sep–Oct 2025): Validate initial findings and **recommendations**.
Prepare for the **Final Plenary on 12 November 2025**

Interested to join a WG?

Link: <https://din.one/display/RISERS>

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